

The effect of *n*-alkyl xanthates on mushroom tyrosinase activity

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Abstract : The effect of three iso-alkyldithiocarbonates (xanthates), as sodium salts, $C_3H_7OCS_2Na$, $C_4H_9OCS_2Na$, $C_5H_{11}OCS_2Na$ and mushroom tyrosinase enzyme, MT, have been investigated by isothermal titration calorimetry, ITC, to clarify thermodynamics of these bindings as well as structural changes of the enzyme due to its interaction with xanthates at 300 K in phosphate buffer (10 mmol L⁻¹; pH 6.8). The extended solvation model was used to elucidate the effect of these xanthates on the stability of the enzyme. The obtained results indicate that there are two identical and non-cooperative binding sites for the three xanthates.

Keywords : Mushroom tyrosinase, iso-propyl xanthate, iso-butyl xanthate, iso-pentyl xanthate.

Introduction

Tyrosinase is ubiquitously distributed among animals, plants and fungi and plays a pivotal role in catalysis of the hydroxylation of monophenols and the oxidation of *o*-diphenols to *o*-diquinones¹. Tyrosinase is responsible for enzymatic browning reactions in damaged fruits during post-harvest handling and processing. Neither hyperpigmentation in human skin nor enzymatic browning in fruits are desirable. Browning after harvest is a common phenomenon in crops such as mushrooms, which decreases the commercial value of the products. Hyperpigmentation in human skin and enzymatic browning in fruits are not desirable. These phenomena have encouraged researchers to seek new potent tyrosinase inhibitors for use in antibrowning of foods and skin whitening. Some tyrosinase inhibitors have been discovered^{2,3}. Tyrosinases are important subjects of many ongoing researches mainly due to their key role in the enzymatic browning phenomenon which affects the quality of fruits, vegetables and crop products⁴. The inhibitors of this enzyme have been utilized in cosmetics, especially as depigmenting agents in the case of hyperpigmentation^{5,6}. The enzymatic browning in fruit and fungi is undesirable in, for example, fresh

fruits, beverages, vegetables and mushrooms^{3,4}. To see whether three new *n*-alkyl xanthates (iso-propyl, iso-butyl and iso-pentyl xanthate) induced structural changes of tyrosinase and how thermodynamical changes by ligand binding are occurred, the extended solvation model was used to analyze of isothermal titration calorimetric data.

Materials and method :

Mushroom tyrosinase was purchased from Sigma and iso-propyl xanthate, iso-butyl xanthate, iso-pentyl xanthate sodium salts were synthesized. All other materials and reagents were of analytical grade, and solutions were made in 10 mmol L⁻¹ buffer phosphate using double-distilled water.

The isothermal titration calorimetric experiments were performed with the four channel commercial calorimetric system, Thermal Activity Monitor 2277, Thermometric, Sweden. Injection of iso-propyl, iso-butyl or iso-pentyl xanthate solution was repeated 20 times by use of a Hamilton syringe into the calorimetric titration vessel, which contained 1.8 mL tyrosinase (8.3 μmol L⁻¹) and phosphate buffer solution (10 mmol L⁻¹; pH 6.8). Each injection included 20 μL xanthate solution. The measurements were performed at constant temperature of 27 °C.

The heat of each injection was calculated by the “Thermometric Digitam 3” software. The heats of interactions between three xanthates with MT against the xanthates concentrations have been shown in Fig. 1 in kJ mol⁻¹ of MT.

Results and discussion

The interaction between a protein and ligand in the aqueous solvent system can be analyzed by the extended solvation equation⁷⁻¹⁶ :

$$q = q_{\max}x'_B - \delta_A^\theta (x'_A L_A + x'_B L_B) - (\delta_B^\theta - \delta_A^\theta)(x'_A L_A + x'_B L_B)x'_B \quad (1)$$

x'_B is a fraction of bound ligand with MT molecule and x'_A is the fraction of unbound ligand. Where x'_B and x'_A can be defined as follows :

$$x'_B = \frac{px_B}{x_A + px_B} \quad x'_A = 1 - x'_B \quad (2)$$

If the ligand binds at each site independently, the binding is non-cooperative. $p > 1$ or $p < 1$ indicate positive or negative cooperativity of a macromolecule for binding with a ligand, respectively; $p = 1$ indicates that the binding is non-cooperative. x_B is equal to the concentration of xanthates after every injection, [Xanthates], divided by the maximum concentration of the xanthates, [Xanthates]_{max}, upon saturation of all MT as follows :

$$x_B = \frac{[\text{Xanthates}]}{[\text{Xanthates}]_{\max}} \quad (3)$$

L_A and L_B are the relative contributions of unbound and bound ligand in the heats of dilution with the exclusion of enzyme and can be calculated from the heats of dilution of ligands in buffer as follows :

$$L_A = q_{\text{dilut}} + x_B \left(\frac{\partial q_{\text{dilut}}}{\partial x_B} \right)$$

$$L_B = q_{\text{dilut}} - x_A \left(\frac{\partial q_{\text{dilut}}}{\partial x_B} \right) \quad (4)$$

Recovered values of δ_A^θ and δ_B^θ from the coefficients of the second and third terms of eq. (1), are indexes of MT structural changes due to the reaction with xanthates in the low and high concentrations, respectively. The negative values of δ_A^θ and δ_B^θ exhibit that iso-propyl, iso-butyl and iso-pentyl xanthates destabilize MT structure. It is possible to attribute the approximately identical values of δ_A^θ and δ_B^θ for iso-propyl xanthate (Table 1) to the mixed inhibition, whereas the different δ_A^θ and δ_B^θ values for iso-butyl and iso-pentyl xanthate (Table 1) can be related to the competitive manner of inhibition. These interpretations are in agreement with previous reports^{3,4}.

A simple graphical method was applied for ITC data analysis in the protein-ligand interaction for a set of identical and independent binding sites to provide the number of binding sites (g), the dissociation binding constant (K_d) and the molar enthalpy of binding site (ΔH°). Using eq. (5) :

$$\frac{\Delta q}{q_{\max}} M_0 = \left(\frac{\Delta q}{q} \right) L_0 \frac{1}{g} - \frac{K_d}{g} \quad (5)$$

M_0 and L_0 are total concentrations of enzyme and ligand, respectively. While q represents the heat value at a certain L_0 and q_{\max} indicates the heat value upon saturation of all the enzyme, $\Delta q = q_{\max} - q$.

The linearity of the plot has been examined by different estimated values for q_{\max} to find the best value for the correlation coefficient. If q_{\max} is calculated per mole of

Table 1. Binding parameters for xanthates + MT interactions recovered from eqs. (1), (5), (6) and (7). $p = 1$ indicates that the binding is non-cooperative in two binding sites. The negative values of δ_A^θ and δ_B^θ show that xanthates destabilize the MT structure. The binding process for MT inhibition is both enthalpy and entropy-driven but the electrostatic interactions are more important than hydrophobic forces

Parameters	I	II	III
p	1 ± 0.01	1 ± 0.01	1 ± 0.01
g	2 ± 0.02	2 ± 0.02	2 ± 0.02
K_a (M ⁻¹)	$9.07 \times 10^4 \pm 24$	$1.26 \times 10^5 \pm 12$	$1.68 \times 10^5 \pm 12$
ΔH° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-18.70 ± 0.06	-19.30 ± 0.07	-1.16 ± 0.03
ΔG° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-28.47 ± 0.12	-29.28 ± 0.14	-30.02 ± 0.13
ΔS° (kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	0.03 ± 0.01	0.03 ± 0.01	0.10 ± 0.02
δ_A^θ	-4.99 ± 0.02	-4.47 ± 0.06	-4.23 ± 0.06
δ_B^θ	-4.23 ± 0.02	-6.58 ± 0.08	-8.66 ± 0.08

enzyme then the standard molar enthalpy of binding for each binding site will be $\Delta H^\circ = \frac{q_{\max}}{g}$.

The change of the standard Gibbs free energy of binding (ΔG°) is determined by using the association binding constant (K_a), obtained from the inverse of K_d value, in the eq. (6), where R is the gas constant and T is the absolute temperature :

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_a \quad (6)$$

The change in standard entropy (ΔS°) of this binding can be calculated as eq. (7) :

$$\Delta S^\circ = \frac{\Delta H^\circ - \Delta G^\circ}{T} \quad (7)$$

All calculated thermodynamic parameters are reported in Table 1.

The thermodynamic parameters for the interaction of the three xanthates with MT (Table 1) indicate that the xanthates + MT complexes can spontaneously form in the buffer solution through both enthalpy and entropy-driven. The value of ΔH is mainly decided by two factors : (a) the polar groups of ligand molecules and those on the surface of protein molecules partly destroy their hydration layers when the ligand molecules approach to the macromolecules, which cause endothermic effect, (b) directly electrostatic interaction of dipole groups of the ligand molecules with peptide sections of protein molecules,

which causes exothermic effect. The experimentally positive enthalpy change indicates that factor (a) is stronger than factor (b) for this type of binding. The change in entropy of the binding process may mainly depend on the direct interaction between the hydrophilic groups of the macromolecules and the ligand molecules, or the hydrophobic interaction of the ligand molecule with the inner part of the binding site. The combined water molecules, including those from the cavities in the macromolecules, release to buffer medium. The first interaction leads to decrease in entropy, while the latter one leads to opposite change in entropy. By considering the two aspects together, it could be easily understood that, the latter factor becomes dominant for this type of binding.

The obtained results indicate that there are two independent and identical binding sites for xanthates + MT interactions and the negative value of molar enthalpy (Table 1) and the positive value of molar entropy suggest that the binding process is both enthalpy and entropy-driven (Table 1) but the electrostatic forces are more important than the hydrophobic ones.

Conclusion :

The extended solvation theory was used to predict enzyme destabilization and non-cooperativity of the interaction in the two identical binding sites. The close agreement is found between the calculated and experimental results (Fig. 1) and gives considerable support to

Fig. 1. Comparison between the experimental heats, q , for the interaction between MT and iso-propyl xanthate (\square), iso-butyl xanthate (Δ) and iso-pentyl xanthate (\circ) at 27 °C and calculated data (lines) via eq. (1).

the use of the extended solvation model. The binding processes for three xanthates are spontaneous in the forward direction ($\Delta G^\circ < 0$). The binding process for MT inhibition is both enthalpy and entropy-driven but the electrostatic interactions are more important than hydrophobic forces. In the other hand, negative δ_A^θ and δ_B^θ values, indicating that three xanthates destabilize MY structure, are the indexes of MT inhibition too. It is possible to attribute the equal values of δ_A^θ and δ_B^θ for iso-propyl xanthate (Table 1) to the mixed inhibition, whereas the different δ_A^θ and δ_B^θ values for iso-butyl and iso-pentyl xanthate (Table 1) can be related to the competitive manner of inhibition.

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